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A Concise Review on the Emerging Field of In-Ear Acoustics Biometrics User Authentication

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ABSTRACT

User Authentication have been for long a well-known standard practice in securing personal and commercial applications be they hardware and/or software solutions to mitigate against potential risks revolving around data privacy and access control. In the times past and even the present moment, the use of password and simple logins persisted. However, the evolving field of smart computing including the rapid growth of advanced sensor based technologies has led to the rise of biometric-capable user authentication systems. These systems add an extra layer of security to the standard simple authenticators including the use of one or more biometric traits as face, finger or even voice etc. However, notwithstanding this additional benefit, the existing biometric traits pose a number of issues that mitigate a successful use of biometrics-based user authentication systems. In this study, we present the emerging field of in-ear acoustics based biometrics as a candidate and more efficient user authentication system. We conduct our reviews on the basis of their adopted approach, strengths and weaknesses with particular emphasis on the role of Machine Learning (ML) in the person authentication or identification process.

Keywords:- Biometrics, Data, In-Ear Acoustics, Learning, Security, User Authentication

INTRODUCTION

Security is a critical area in society that is of utmost concern in a diverse number of facilities such as in the banking, supermarkets, residential and commercial facilities etc. This affects the persons operating such facilities, as the need to safeguard their business operations is paramount to the success of their business. This particular security function is most often tied to the data and/or information which the business owners themselves might be vulnerable to.

In this regard, data and information security has become one of the most pressing challenges confronting all kinds of present day organizations owing to their rapid adoption of information technology (IT) in the entirety of their activities.

This development has made data and information to a larger extent vulnerable to unauthorized users, spammers, crawlers and hackers who break into business organization's data privacy and when granted access steal valuable info and in certain situations physical assets. In particular, this has posed greater challenges on people who use database, share files and other resources on computer networks (Cherdantseva & Hilton, 2013).

Information transmission through internet may include sensitive personal data which may be intercepted. Also, there are many applications on the internet and many web sites require the users to fill forms that include sensitive personal information such as telephone numbers, addresses, and credit card information. So, the users may need private and secure communications for many reasons such as protect their confidential information from hackers during it passed over an open channel, so the confidentiality and data integrity are required to protect against unauthorized access and use.

Hence, the development of user authentication currently emphasizes the use of biometrics as an added layer of security to enhance the robustness and tolerance to emerging threats. Some of such popular biometrics-based solutions include the use of facial and fingerprint image captures or scans to authenticate a person as genuine (Minaee et al., 2021). But as addressed in some related studies, these biometric face several pressing issues bordering on the tamper-resistance and image doctoring (Yang et al., 2019; Zhao et al., 2021).

While the research in biometrics based user authentication systems is very broad and active, this study attempts to provide a more focused approach by reviewing related studies that border primarily on in-ear biometrics based user authentication system. In particular, the key research studies on in-ear acoustics are reviewed and their strengths and weaknesses equally discussed.

Some very vital considerations for real-time user authentication that exploits in-ear biometrics are as summarized below:

1. Ability to respond in a fast and timely manner.
2. Implement behavioral trait capture features for Continuous User Authentication (CUA) (Stylios *et al.*, 2021).
3. Considering the real-time applications, the ML system adopted should be adaptable and learn continually in order to support the CUA (Osegi, 2023).

In the sections that follow, we present some of the emerging studies in this very important area and provide a summary of some key research directions. We generate these studies following specific search commands with the Google search engine. In particular, a total of 50 search requests were performed with the keyword "In-Ear

Acoustics Biometrics User Authentication” which was further fine-tuned to include the search criteria “ML”, “Machine Learning” and/or “Continual Learning” from which a reduction to about 15 research articles were arrived at.

Finally, we conclude with discussions on salient points and propose some future research directions.

EMERGING STUDIES IN IN-EAR ACOUSTICS BIOMETRIC USER AUTHENTICATION

Research in the use of in-ear acoustics based biometric user authentication systems though limited, presents an active area where several studies have been conducted in diverse disciplines. This is due to distinguishing feature of human beings basing on their physical and personal characteristics eliminating the aforementioned problems in existing image based biometrics solutions (Casanova *et al.*, 2021).

Earlier studies on biometric authentication used the Fisher Linear Discriminant Analysis (FDLA) and non-FDLA (n-FDLA) for a set of 31 subjects and using 8 ear transfer functions for earphones and headphones platforms and 17 subjects for mobile phone platforms (Akkermans *et al.*, 2005a, 2005b).

Fast person authentication system simulator considering commercially available artificial earbuds for microphone signal probing and a tri-feature vector representation have been investigated in (Arakawa *et al.*, 2016). Cosine similarity results considering the mel-frequency cepstral coefficient (MFCC), Ear Canal Impulse Response (ECIR), Ear Canal Transfer Function (ECTF) with FDLA measures for 30 subjects were reported considering 3 feature representations. Their results showed that the ECIR gave

best EER values followed with the ECTF and MFCC.

Xu *et al* (2019) proposed a behavioral biometric approach (*AcousticID*) based on gait-traits and acoustic signaling for human authentication. They used 256-dimension gait features which were extracted from the acoustic signals for a group of 50 persons. They reported high recognition accuracy of about 96.6% using Support Vector Machine (SVM) for person identification.

In Alsawwaf & Chaczko (2020), the potentials of ear acoustics for biometric authentication have been discussed with reference to prior studies conducted in (Liu & Hatzinakos, 2014a; Liu & Hatzinakos, 2014b) with respect to biometric modalities and hashing functionalities.

Mahto *et al* (2018) proposed an in-ear acoustics biometric system that exploits the presence of in-audible probe signals for acoustic feature representation and capture. Their proposed system used primarily a three-tier feature extraction (signal recording/data capture) process including the Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) to obtain the two components of the Discrete Fourier Transform (DFT), the Cross Spectral Density (CSD) to obtain the ear canal transfer function and the mel-frequency Cepstral Coefficient (MFCC) to obtain the intra-class invariant feature representations while considering fixed and variable earphone positioning.

Using a max-score metric based on a trio-enrollment evaluator procedure, the reported percent EER for inaudible signals were better than audible one for a continuous authentication test. On the other hand, for the initial authentication test, the percent EER was found to be lower for the audible signals when compared to inaudible signals case.

In (Sulavko *et al.*, 2021) the use of cepstral analysis with energy-based feature dimensionality reduction (CEPEB), Naïve Bayesian (NB), and Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) – convolutional and standard ANN for acoustics-based ear recognition studies on 75 human subjects have been proposed and developed. For the CEPEB, the distinguishing features considered the reflected signal average amplitude parameters and cepstrogram parameters.

Also, considering several signal processing windowing functions, it was found that the combination of the Hamming and Rectangular windows gave best EER results for CEPEB. The results of classification using CEPEB features with the NB and ANN techniques showed that the NB technique showed a lower identification errors i.e. lower Equal Error Rate (EER) at 0.0053 while the best possible EER obtained by ANN techniques was much higher at 0.0266. Also, the BN technique reported very low False Acceptance Rate (FAR) at values much less than 0.0001 and reasonable False Rejection Rate (FRR) at 0.1028.

Yasuhara *et al* (2022a) proposed the use of SVM technique for classification of real time data obtained from in-earphone acoustics-based biometrics. They extracted features on bilateral (left-right ear) data

considering three novel concepts – the additive, subtractive and concatenative featuring operations. Graphical results considering Equal Error Rate (EER) and Area Under Curve (AUC) evaluation metrics and under two test sessions showed that the concatenated operation gave the least EER and best AUC.

Also, in Yasuhara et al (2022b), the SVM classifier is employed in a sickit-learn simulation environment and utilized for between-class (BC) features classification. The BC featurization is based on a combination of samples of authorized and un-authorized features for which their ratio is constrained between 0 and 1 using a known mathematical formula. Thus, BC featurization may be regarded as an intermediate feature synthesis operation. The results of simulation tests considering real time datasets using similar scheme as in Yasuhara *et al* (2022a) showed that the FRR can be reduced by 7.95% while the EER was reduced by at most 0.15%.

SUMMARY OF KEY RELATED WORKS

Research in the field of in-ear biometrics as discussed in Section 2 is summarized as provided in Table 1. This captures the existing approaches including the potential strengths as well as weaknesses of the research studies.

Table 1:- Overview of Selected In-Ear Biometrics Research Approaches

S/N	AUTHOR	ADOPTED APPROACH	STRENGTH OF THE WORK	WEAKNESS OF THE WORK
1	Akkermans <i>et al.</i> , 2005a	In-ear person identification using Fisher Linear Discriminant Analysis (FDLA) and non-FDLA (n-FDLA) method	Presents simple identification classifier.	Large errors. Lack of Continual ML Capabilities.
2	Akkermans <i>et al.</i> , 2005b	In-ear person identification using Fisher Linear Discriminant Analysis (FDLA) and non-FDLA (n-FDLA) method	Presents simple identification classifier.	Large errors reported. Lack of Continual ML Capabilities.

3	Arakawa <i>et al.</i> , 2016	Investigative Research using a fast person authentication system simulator with cosine similarity measure and considering the Ear Canal Impulse Response (ECIR), Ear Canal Transfer Function (ECTF) and mel-frequency cepstral coefficient (MFCC).	Speed of processing.	Absence of ML/AI processing logic. Lack of Continual Learning Capabilities.
4	Xu <i>et al</i> (2019)	Investigative research employing behavioral acoustic-signal driven gait-based patterns based on the use of SVM for person identification.	Enhanced featurization using hybridized solution	Bias may be introduced by the acoustic signaling mode. Lack of Continual Learning Capabilities
5	Alsawwaf & Chaczko (2020)	Reviews on ear acoustics for biometric authentication	Specific reviews of in-ear acoustics including fingerprinting and signature verification captured.	Absence of studies on AI/ML techniques.
6	Mahto <i>et al</i> (2018)	Investigative research where the authors proposed an in-ear acoustics biometric system that exploits the presence of in-audible probe signals for acoustic feature representation and capture using a using a max-score metric.	Simple scoring enhances speed of response.	Lack of Continual Learning Capabilities.
7	Sulavko <i>et al.</i> , 2021	Investigative research using cepstral analysis with energy-based feature dimensionality reduction (CEPEB), Naïve Bayesian (NB), and Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) – convolutional and standard ANN for acoustics-based ear recognition.	Hybridization makes for best form model selection.	Supervision requiring need for class labels. Large data requirement. Lack of Continual Learning Capabilities.
8	Yasuhara <i>et al</i> (2022a)	SVM technique for classification of real time data obtained from in-earphone acoustics-based biometrics	With proper design SVM presents a very fast and accurate solution.	Supervision requiring need for class labels. Lack of Continual Learning Capabilities.
9	Yasuhara <i>et al</i> (2022b)	SVM classifier employed in a sickit-learn simulation environment for BC features classification.	With proper design SVM presents a very fast and accurate solution.	Supervision requiring need for class labels. Lack of Continual Learning Capabilities.

While the desirable properties such as simple identification classifier is present in in-ear acoustics based solutions, issues such as the presence of large recognition errors are identified in item 1 and 2 in addition to lacking Continual Learning (CL) capabilities – an important requirement for real-time Machine Learning (ML) based biometric user authentication systems which is clearly absent in these model approaches.

The approaches in items 4, and 7-9 employ strictly supervised label-driven ML solutions for user authentication (person identification) and hence suffer from the real-time re-calibration problem. The implication is that such model approaches in the long-run are more time-expensive as they need to be recalibrated with every change during in-ear acoustics capture.

DISCUSSIONS AND CONCLUSION

As seen from the reviewed works, the studies on in-ear acoustics based biometrics user authentication systems employed techniques that include both ML and non-ML solutions. In the specific areas of ML based solutions, the NB, SVM and ANN techniques are identified.

Notwithstanding the benefits of simplicity and fast response, the emerging ML in-ear biometrics based user authentication approaches are still lacking the continual learning capability. Hence, this presents a promising area for research explorations.

Also, noted is the absence of research in the field of limited data analysis based on continual ML systems for in-ear acoustics based biometrics. Thus, further research in this area to determine the existence of such studies should be conducted. In particular, in the absence of such studies, it is recommended that the biometric engineering researcher conduct studies in this very important topic area.

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